

The Effect of Methyl and Halogen Substituents on the U. V. Spectra of Quinoline and Iso-Quinoline

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In two previous communications^{1,2} it has been shown that Longuet-Higgins and Sowden's³ perturbation calculations on the longest wave length spectral shift of some Aza-aromatics due to methyl and halogen substitution agree fairly closely with the experimental values. In the present paper, the results of investigations on Quinoline and Iso-quinoline are reported.

The mathematical procedure has been described in our previous communications^{1,2}. The molecular orbital energies and atomic orbital coefficients for Quinoline and Iso-quinoline have been taken from Coulson and Streitwieser⁴ with $\alpha_N = \alpha + 0.5\beta$ and $\beta_{CN} = \beta$ and the values for all other quantities, used here, are same as in our previous communications.

The results are set out in Table I, where the column headed by $\Delta\lambda$ is the energy difference converted into wave length taking $\beta = -23000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

DISCUSSION

On examination of Table I, it is found that the inductive and hyperconjugative (conjugative) effect may be bathochromic or hypsochromic, but the calculated resultant effect is always bathochromic, except for 2-methyl quinoline, where the resultant effect is hypsochromic. Whenever the inductive effect is hypsochromic, the hyperconjugative (conjugative) effect is bathochromic or vice versa, and in some cases both the effects are bathochromic; but in no case both the effects are hypsochromic. In some cases, the two effects almost neutralize each other resulting in a very small shift, which indeed, is the case with 2-fluoroquinoline. The present calculation shows that the resultant shifts for most of the compounds will be bathochromic, which is actually the case; however there are certain exception, viz., 2-fluoroquinoline and 1-fluoro-iso-quinoline show a slight hypsochromic shift, whereas the calculated shift is bathochromic. In case of 8-methyl-, 8-chloro-8-bromo -and 8-fluoroquinolines, the calculated bathochromic shifts are too high.

Considering the simplicity of the method, the agreement between the calculated and experimental results is quite satisfactory. In certain cases where the experimental data are not available. the calculated values may be considered as the predicted spectral shifts.

1. B. Majee and B. K. Das, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 1086.
2. B. Das, *ibid.*, 1968, **45**, 1075.
3. H. C. Longuet-Higgins and R. G. Sowden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 9152, 1404.
4. C. A. Coulson and A. Strietwieser, "Dictionary of electron Calculations" (Pergamon Press, London), 1965, p. 297, 302.

TABLE I

Compound	$\frac{(\Delta E_{ba}) \text{ induc.}}{\beta}$	$\frac{(\Delta E_{ba}) \text{ hyperconj. or conj.}}{\beta}$	$\frac{(\Delta E_{ba}) \text{ total}}{\beta}$	$\Delta\lambda(\text{Cal.})m\mu$	$\Delta\lambda(\text{Obs.})m\mu$
Quinoline, $E_b - E_a = -1.2304\beta$, $\lambda_{max} = 313 m\mu$ (in ten per cent ethanol)*					
2-methyl-	-0.00922	+0.00339	-0.00586	-1.7	2
3- "	+0.00281	+0.00877	+0.01158	3.3	5
4- "	-0.00951	+0.01511	+0.00550	1.5	0
5- "	+0.00661	+0.02437	+0.03098	9.0	...
6- "	+0.00495	+0.01030	+0.01525	4.4	4
7- "	-0.00051	+0.00722	+0.00671	3.1	5
8- "	+0.00992	+0.02596	+0.03584	10.5	1
2-Chloro-	+0.01020	-0.00546	+0.00474	1.3	5
3- "	-0.00216	+0.01416	+0.01200	3.5	10
4- "	+0.00993	+0.01048	+0.02041	5.9	3
5- "	-0.00627	+0.03968	+0.03341	9.99	4
6- "	+0.00363	+0.01840	+0.02203	6.4	6
7- "	+0.00169	+0.00866	+0.01035	2.9	6
8- "	-0.00952	+0.04515	+0.03563	10.5	2
2-Bromo-	+0.00704	-0.00271	+0.00423	1.2	6
3- "	-0.00122	+0.01218	+0.01096	3.1	10
4- "	+0.00690	+0.01158	+0.01848	5.4	...
5- "	-0.00442	+0.03412	+0.02970	8.7	4
6- "	-0.00268	+0.01552	+0.01284	3.8	7
7- "	+0.00106	+0.00801	+0.00907	2.5	7
8- "	-0.00670	+0.03829	+0.03159	9.3	2
2-Fluoro-	+0.01567	-0.01268	+0.00299	0.8	-1
3- "	-0.00186	+0.01211	+0.01025	2.9	6
4- "	+0.01504	-0.00124	+0.01380	4.0	...
5- "	-0.00927	+0.03430	+0.02503	7.4	1
6- "	-0.00496	+0.01708	+0.01212	3.5	3
7- "	+0.00297	+0.00525	+0.08199	2.3	3
8- "	-0.01413	+0.04188	+0.02705	7.8	0
Iso-quinoline, $E_b - E_a = -1.2220\beta$, $\lambda_{max} = 319m\mu$ (in ethanol)*					
1-Methyl-	-0.01013	+0.01600	+0.00587	1.8	...
3- "	+0.00948	+0.01230	+0.02148	6.4	...
4- "	+0.00283	+0.02040	+0.02323	6.8	...
5- "	+0.00486	+0.02130	+0.02616	7.8	...
6- "	-0.00331	+0.00580	+0.00249	0.8	...
7- "	-0.00386	+0.00960	+0.00574	1.7	...
8- "	-0.00065	+0.01910	+0.01845	5.5	...

TABLE I (Contd.)

Compound	(ΔE_{ba}) induc.	(ΔE_{ba}) hyperconj. or conj.	(ΔE_{ba}) total	$\Delta\lambda(\text{Cal.})m\mu$	$\Delta\lambda(\text{Obs.})m\mu$
	β	β	β		
1-Fluoro-	+0.01498	-0.00140	+0.01358	4.0	-1
3- ,,	-0.01338	+0.02730	+0.01392	4.1	0
4- ,,	-0.00320	+0.02370	+0.02050	6.1	2
5- ,,	-0.00617	+0.02790	+0.02170	6.4	...
6- ,,	+0.00664	-0.00160	+0.00504	1.5	...
7- ,,	+0.00779	+0.01640	+0.02419	7.2	...
8- ,,	+0.00191	+0.01680	+0.01871	5.5	...
1-Chloro-	+0.00999	+0.00960	+0.01959	5.9	5
3- ,,	-0.00980	+0.02545	+0.01637	4.9	10
4- ,,	-0.00227	+0.02850	+0.02623	7.8	5
5- ,,	-0.00426	+0.03180	+0.02754	8.2	7
6- ,,	+0.00437	+0.00280	+0.00718	2.3	1
7- ,,	+0.00493	+0.01670	+0.02163	6.4	10
8- ,,	+0.00115	+0.02330	+0.02445	7.2	7
1-Bromo-	+0.00701	+0.01290	+0.01991	5.9	...
3- ,,	-0.00643	+0.02040	+0.01397	4.1	...
4- ,,	-0.00155	+0.02440	+0.02285	6.8	...
5- ,,	-0.00304	+0.02690	+0.02386	7.2	...
6- ,,	+0.00305	+0.00330	+0.00635	2.0	...
7- ,,	+0.00333	+0.01370	+0.01703	5.1	...
8- ,,	+0.00073	+0.02060	+0.02133	6.4	...

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- *5. (a) S. B. Knight, R. H. Wallick and J. Brown, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3780.
 (b) S. B. Knight, R. H. Wallick and C. Blach, *ibid.*, 1955, **77**, 2577.
 (c) W. K. Miller, S. B. Knight and A. Roe, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 1629.
 (d) S. B. Knight, W. K. Miller, and A. Roe, *ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 1599.
 (e) J. P. Phillips and F. C. Nachod, "Organic electronic spectral data", (Interscience Publishers, London) 1963, Vol. IV, p. 192.